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**Fertility in the Vlachic population of Greece:
 a demo-anthropological approach of Metsovo,
 1930-1999 with the application of a genealogy based
 method of analysis.**

1. INTRODUCTION

While the fertility trends in Greece during the 20th century are very well documented and analyzed (see for example Siampos, 1990; Siampos, 1994; Kotzamanis *et al.*, 1994; Kotzamanis, 2006), studies of local populations are rare. Some examples of such works are those of Hionidou (1993), who studied fertility transition in Mykonos (1859-1959) and of Gavalas (2002) who studied two villages of the Island of Paros. Also, Hatzisavva and Xiroteris (2003) have published a preliminary study of the genealogical and demographic characteristics of the Vlachic Population of Metsovo (Epirus, Greece) and Zafeiris and Xiroteris (2007) have studied the demographic and genealogical structure of the Vlachic Population of Karitsa (Pieria) and also of a Roma population in Greek Thrace (2002). Bournova (1995) has published some elements of the historical demography and everyday life of Rapsani and Caftanzoglou (1994, 1997, 1997b) some demographic information about Sirkako, focusing on kinship, domestic organization and family formation system.

In this paper - based on the same data used in Hatzisavva's and Xiroteris's publication (2003) - a more detailed analysis of the fertility of Metsovo will be carried out. Metsovo is located in the Region of Epirus (Map 1), 419 Km away from Athens (de facto population: 1928: 2156, 1951: 2798, resident population 2001: 2963 persons, 1489 males and 1474 females; SGG, 1933; SNG, 1955; NSSG, 2009). It is one of the historical settlements, of the Aromuns (Vlachs) of Greece (see also Koukoudis, 2000).

Historical Metsovo was subdivided into two major areas, named *ano* (*upper*) and *kato* (*lower*) *mahala*, let's say upper and lower vicinities, on either side of the main street of the town. Between them another, smaller neighborhood was located, almost in the center of the city (Map 2). This historical division of the town into larger vicinities and smaller parishes/neighborhoods depended on the geographic and environmental characteristics of

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the area and reflected the spatial distribution of the inhabitants according to their occupations and the social stratification of the town. The Pastoralists lived in the upper part of the town, the traders – the wealthiest part of the population - lived in the middle of the town and the “occupational groups” (barrel-makers, saddlers, woodcarvers, carpenters, coopers, etc.) lived in “*kato mahala*”.

Map 1 – Map of Greece

Map 2 – Spatial distribution of the professional groups in Metsovo

The original data source is the archive of the Civil Register Office of the Municipality of Metsovo. However, instead of the common practice of simply analyzing statistically these archive data, a new method of data manipulation in combination with exhaustive field work was developed in order for the data to be crosschecked, evaluated and enriched. This method is described in detail in the Methods section. There are two main questions addressed in this paper. The first deals with the quantitative analysis of fertility’s levels and temporal trends from a period and cohort perspective. The second deals with

the examination of any fertility differentials that may exist among the different spatial/occupational population groups living in the town.

2. METHODS AND DATA

The available data published from the National Statistical Service of Greece for Metsovo is not sufficient in order for the fertility trends - from either period or cohort perspective - to be analyzed during the whole 20th century as the population structure is not published in the results of older censuses.

In such cases it is quite common to apply several family reconstitution methods (Fleury and Henry, 1956; Wrigley, 1966; Henry, 1980; Newton, 2011) in which scattered data from parish registers or perhaps from other sources, like the Civil Register Archives, concerning baptism, marriage and burials etc. are linked together in order for the demographic history of individuals and their families to be reconstructed (see for example Bengtsson and Dribe, 2014). These methods have been extensively used by historical demographers in Europe and North America, where numerous parish registers are available (Levine, 2003). However, it has to be noted that migration (except perhaps some of its forms like the marital one) cannot be taken into consideration so that population flows cannot be estimated. This may cause problems in calculations of the conventional occurrence/exposure demographic rates of typical demography, like the Age Specific Fertility rates and the Total Fertility Rate (for the rates see Preston *et al.*, 2001, pp. 3 and 95). Therefore, an alternative methodology was applied, already used in relevant analysis of fertility in the Roma of Thrace (Zafeiris and Xirotiris, 2002), in the Pomaks (Zafeiris, 2006), the Vlachs of Karitsa (Zafeiris and Xirotiris, 2007) and elsewhere.

In fact, the direct application of the typical family reconstitution methods discussed above is not necessary as the Registrar General of the Civil Register Office of Metsovo, which was used as a primary data source, is already a family register archive. Each family registry contains demographic information about the father, the mother and the children of a nuclear family: birth date, death date, marriage date(s), divorce date(s) etc. Typically, when a child from a family gets married he/she is transcribed to another family registry as head (husband) if it is a male or as a wife if it is a female. In a special column of the book the number of the family of destination is written during this process, while the number of the family of origin is written in another column in the new family registry. It must be noted that the divorced husbands remain as heads of their family in their registry. Women are transcribed to a new family registry as divorced, following the same procedure as above. Formally therefore, a person's position in the archive can be identified by a series of reference numbers consisting of their paternal family number and the number of the family registries in which it has been transcribed. In that way a person can be followed up until their death or deletion because of its transcription following migration to

another municipality. However, because this archive was available only in printed form, the data contained within had to be stored manually in a database specially prepared for that purpose, named Demstat_v2 at this stage of development. Using several methods, the different registries each person had in the Registrar General were connected and finally it was represented by a unique record in the database. All the available demographic information was connected with this record. Thereafter, the old Registrar General, which was developed when Epirus was annexed by Greece in 1912 and the other Civil Register archives (birth, death and marriage books) were used in order for the data to be enriched. Several checking and cross checking procedures were used during this process.

Figure 1 – Patrilineal genealogical tree or pedigree

Then the patrilineal genealogical trees of the population were constructed. Genealogies have been extensively used as a source for demographic research (see for example Zhao, 2001, where an overview of the literature is cited), but in this project they served as a major research tool during the subsequent field work. By definition, a genealogy shows the genealogical relationships and the lines of descent of the family, in our case following the paternal lines. These trees were enriched with demographic information as shown in Figure 1, but during demographic analysis they were transformed into pedigrees, in order for only the biological offspring of a woman to be taken into consideration and not any adopted children she may have had which were admeasured to their biological mothers.

Using these genealogies as a basic research tool, an exhaustive field work was carried out by a research team headed by one of us (Nov. 1999 - May 2000 and Jul. 2001 - Aug. 2001). With the aid of informants from every family living in Metsovo and any kind of available family personal archives and documents, the recorded genealogical relationships of the members of the population were screened out and checked for their consistency. A key goal of the field work was the clarification of the dates of the demographic events, as well as the filling in of missing data, such as unrecorded people, births, deaths, migrations, genealogical relationships etc. This was necessary as the geographic mobility of the population was high in the past and it had to be checked if any demographic events were not recorded. Also, permanent migration had to be recorded because any official archives concerning migration in Greece are absent. In that way the archives contained people that had permanently migrated to other places in the past, while there was a possibility that some people living in Metsovo were not registered in the Civil Register Archives. Using close relatives (for example the father, the mother or a sibling of a migrant) or even the migrant himself as informants, we were able to identify migration with one year precision. During the statistical analysis immigrants and emigrants were considered to have migrated in the middle of the year of their migration. Also, we found that the husbands and wives born in other places used to move to Metsovo by the time of their marriage, and thus they were considered as members of the resident population of the town since that time. Questionnaires were additionally used for the identification of the households of the town in the past and the examination of their historical development, size, composition and spatial location. Finally, through semi-structured interviews collective and individual memories were recorded in order for life in traditional Metsovo to be reconstructed.

The final number of the pedigrees constructed was 129 (7,932 persons) distributed, according to their genealogical depth, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 – *Number of pedigrees of the population of Metsovo by genealogical depth*

Number of generations contained in the pedigrees	Number of pedigrees
10	1
9	1
8	6
7	24
6	43
5	44
Less than 5	10
Total	129

After updating the database, the life lines of the members of the population were constructed and the analysis of fertility took place. By tabulating these life lines in the well known Lexis Diagram (see Feeney, 2003), the relevant person years of the female population at risk for procreation for a period of time or a cohort could be estimated. Immigration and emigration were taken into consideration as they were fully recorded at personal level during field work. In other words, both the number of occurrences of demographic events and the person-years of exposure to the risk of occurrence of these events were available in order for conventional fertility rates to be calculated (see Preston *et al.*, 2001, pp. 3). Then, a period and cohort analysis of the Total Fertility Rates (*TFRs* and *cTFRs* respectively) was carried out for the total population of the town. Subsequently, the *TFRs* of the different spatial groups of the population were calculated. All calculations were based on the known formula:

$$TFR = 5 * \sum_a^b asfr$$

where *asfr* stands for the Age Specific Fertility rates (Preston *et al.*, 2001, p. 95). Due to the small size of the population, five year-long periods and birth cohorts of women were used because year by year analysis was subject to chance fluctuations. Age-specific fertility rates were calculated as the quotient of births which took place in the town to the total number of person-years of the women spent in each age class for every period and birth cohort. The *TFRs* and *cTFRs* were decomposed into two components, i.e. the fertility of women aged less than 30 years and that of the women aged 30 years or over. All calculations were made with Demstat v2.

Then the same calculations were applied for the different birth orders following the Bongaarts and Feeney methodology (1998), in order to estimate the

contribution of births of each order to the overall observed fertility. Obviously $TFR = \sum TFR_i$, where i is the birth order. For each of them the mean age at childbearing (MAC) was calculated from the period fertility distribution using the usual midpoint approximation per age class of women. MAC for all births was calculated as the weighted average of MAC per birth order as follows:

$$MAC = MAC_1w_1 + MAC_2w_2 + MAC_3w_3 + MAC_4w_4 + MAC_{+4}w_{+4},$$

where $w_i = TFR_i / TFR$. The importance of MAC changes regarding the observed fertility levels is significant, because when age at childbearing of successive cohorts of women declines TFR inflates and the opposite happens when the cohorts are delaying childbearing (Bongaarts, 1999).

Finally, the temporal fertility trends among the different occupational-spatial groups described in the introduction of the paper were analyzed in order for fertility differentials to be identified. The analysis is based on 75 of the 129 pedigrees of Metsovo, where there was compelling evidence about the main occupation and the original place of residence of their members. These pedigrees were spatially located in the pre-World War II era and then their spatial distribution was screened out against the main occupation of their members, irrespective of any temporal changes in their occupations or parallel professions they had, according to the field work findings. It was found that the original up/down division of the town served very well the analysis except one or two cases of stockbreeders' families, which had moved to the middle of the town. These were included in the upper part of the town - their original place of residence as found in the field work. A third group living in the middle of the town - that of the traders, was initially identified and analyzed separately, but due to its very small population size - and the elevated uncertainty of the findings - they are not included in the following discussion. Women were originally placed in the pedigree of their father if they were unmarried and in the pedigree of their spouse if they were married.

The results for the period analysis of fertility will be cited from 1930-1934 onwards, when no missing births and birthdates of the mothers exist in the database, i.e. when the full coverage of the population was achieved. However, for the cohort fertility it has to be noted that the estimations for the older cohorts are based on sample data. An underestimate of the births cannot be ruled out for these cohorts, despite the vast effort made during the field work. In any case, data were of better quality, and they become even better for the women born after the 1905-09, when full coverage for these cohorts is achieved.

3. RESULTS

Period fertility in Metsovo was high in the 1930s (Table 2). The crucial

point of the fertility transition of the 20th century in Metsovo is the Greek Italian war of 1940, which was followed by the occupation of the country by the Germans and their allies until 1944, and the Greek Civil War of 1946-1949 (see Clogg, 1995, pp.127-151). In those years *TFRs* (Table 2) were about 3.4 children per woman, at least one child less than in the 1930s. Over the next years, period fertility rates gradually converged very close to 2.5 children. Beginning in the 1970s, a new phase of transition limited fertility levels to 1.2 children per woman in 1995-1999. This transition was accompanied by changes in the timetable of births, as the temporal trends of mean age at childbearing (*MAC*) reveal: it declines until 1975-1979 and increases afterwards.

Table 2 – *Period Fertility Rate (TFR) and Average Age at Childbearing (MAC) in Metsovo*

Period	TFR	MAC (all births)	Contribution to TFR of women aged	
			<30 years	>=30 years
1930-1934	4.5	31.3	2.2	2.3
1935-1939	4.4	31.1	2.1	2.3
1940-1944	3.4	30.6	1.6	1.8
1945-1949	3.4	31.5	1.5	2.0
1950-1954	2.8	30.8	1.3	1.5
1955-1959	2.4	29.1	1.4	1.0
1960-1964	2.6	27.8	1.8	0.8
1965-1969	2.5	26.9	1.7	0.7
1970-1974	1.8	26.2	1.5	0.4
1975-1979	1.7	25.4	1.5	0.3
1980-1984	1.6	25.7	1.4	0.3
1985-1989	1.4	26.2	1.1	0.4
1990-1994	1.3	26.2	1.0	0.3
1995-1999	1.2	26.3	0.9	0.3

There is a clear distinction in the reproductive behaviour between the older and the younger women (Table 2). In the 1930s, the contribution of the older women to the *TFR* was high. Afterwards, despite some minor fluctuations, their fertility decreased until the 1970s, when their contribution to the period *TFRs* was only 0.3-0.4 children. The younger women followed a more variable course, until the early 1960s, but later on, they limited their fertility considerably. As a result, women over time gave birth to fewer children.

Table 3 – *Period Fertility Rates (TFR) and Average Age at Childbearing (MAC) in Metsovo by birth order*

Birth order	1		2		3		4		>4	
	TFR	MAC	TFR	MAC	TFR	MAC	TFR	MAC	TFR >	MAC ^
Period										
1930-1934	1.0	25.9	1.1	28.8	1.0	30.5	0.5	33.4	1.0	39.2
1935-1939	0.8	25.9	0.9	27.2	0.9	30.7	0.8	33.3	1.0	37.5
1940-1944	0.7	24.8	0.6	27.8	0.7	31.0	0.5	32.5	0.9	35.9
1945-1949	0.7	26.1	0.7	28.0	0.7	31.7	0.5	33.8	0.9	36.6
1950-1954	0.6	26.4	0.6	27.9	0.5	30.1	0.4	33.9	0.7	36.0
1955-1959	0.8	25.2	0.5	27.8	0.4	30.3	0.3	33.0	0.3	36.4
1960-1964	1.1	25.0	0.9	28.1	0.4	31.7	0.1	31.6	0.1	35.1
1965-1969	1.0	23.5	0.8	27.3	0.5	31.3	0.1	29.8	0.1	34.8
1970-1974	0.6	24.1	0.8	26.1	0.3	27.8	0.1	29.3	0.1	32.9
1975-1979	0.7	22.7	0.6	26.2	0.3	28.4	0.1	29.4	0.0	32.5
1980-1984	0.6	23.5	0.7	25.7	0.2	28.2	0.1	30.1	0.0	33.6
1985-1989	0.5	23.2	0.5	26.2	0.3	28.9	0.1	30.6	0.1	35.1
1990-1994	0.5	24.1	0.5	26.3	0.2	29.2	0.1	28.4	0.0	32.9
1995-1999	0.6	24.6	0.4	26.3	0.2	30.1	0.0	31.3	0.0	30.9

Fertility transition in Metsovo is then connected mainly with the voluntary restraint of family size. This is quite obvious in the results of Table 3: fertility declines as births of higher order decline. For the births of order 3 and higher and despite the observed variability the dominant trend is of the decrease of *TFR* accompanied with rather variable temporal trends of the relevant *MAC*. As a result, these births contributed more than 2.5 children per woman to the overall *TFR* in 1930s and only 0.2 children in 1995-1999. It has to be noted that the postponement of childbearing that is observed for the births of order 3 in the last years of the study may have suppressed somewhat the observed fertility rates. The births of lower order had a more variable but overall decreasing course. However, there the effect of the changes of the time table of births on the observed levels of fertility is clearer. In the first births after 1975-1979 *MAC* increases and this suppresses *TFR* of order 1 at about 0.5-0.6 children. For births of order 2 since the 1970s *MAC* changes are insignificant, but the relevant *TFR* reduced by 0.4 children until 1995-1999, then the quantum of fertility declines even for the births of that order. A similar interplay between *MAC* and period fertility levels has been observed since the first period of the study “adjusting” the levels of observed fertility every time.

Table 4 – Cohort Completed Fertility Rate (cTFR) and Cohort Average Age at Childbearing (cMAC) in Metsovo

Period	cTFR	cMAC (all births)	Contribution to cTFR of women aged	
			<30 years	>=30 years
1885-1889	4.5	32.8	1.7	2.8
1890-1894	4.5	31.8	1.8	2.7
1895-1899	3.8	31.2	1.6	2.2
1900-1904	3.7	31.6	1.6	2.1
1905-1909	4.0	29.8	2.3	1.7
1910-1914	3.9	30.0	2.0	1.8
1915-1919	2.9	29.4	1.6	1.4
1920-1924	2.8	28.6	1.7	1.1
1925-1929	2.0	28.6	1.3	0.7
1930-1934	1.8	27.9	1.3	0.5
1935-1939	2.2	27.5	1.6	0.6
1940-1944	1.8	26.4	1.4	0.4
1945-1949	1.8	25.2	1.5	0.2
1950-1954*	[1.8]		1.5	[0.4]
1955-1959*	[1.7]		1.4	[0.3]
1960-1964*	[1.6]		1.3	[0.4]
1965-1969*	[1.3]		0.9	[0.4]

Note: *Because these cohorts have not completed their fertility by year 1999, in order to calculate the completed fertility rates, age specific rates have been frozen up to the last birth cohort which in each age class all the women participated in it have overpass the upper age limit of this age class by the end of 1999. For Karitsa this estimation refers only to the cohorts of 1960-1964 and 1965-1969.

Cohort completed fertility in Metsovo, after some fluctuations in the older cohorts, diminishes steadily towards the younger ones. Women progressively give birth to fewer children and stop their reproduction at younger ages (Table 4). The maximum fertility for these cohorts, counted by the available data, is 4.5 children per woman. In those which formed between 1895 and 1914 however, the completed fertility fluctuates between 3.7 and 4.0 children, evidence of acceleration of the fertility transition which will become clearer for the women born between 1915 and 1924, whose completed fertility is 2.8-2.9 children per woman. This is nevertheless still far away from the limit of 2.1 children which, given the modern levels of mortality, is thought to be the generation's replacement level. In the subsequent cohorts fertility is gradually limited to 1.8 children per woman, or even less as expected for the cohort who hadn't completed their reproductive life by 2000.

The mechanism of fertility limitation mainly deals with the gradual and voluntary restraint of the upper limit of reproduction of women and the

decrease in the size of their families. In this course, the contribution to the cohort fertility rates of the older ages (more than 30 years) becomes over time less important. From 2.8 for women's birth cohort of 1885-1889 it decreases to only 0.2 children per woman for the cohort of 1945-1949, while average age at childbearing decreases for almost 8 years between these two cohorts. The contribution of the younger ages is more variable, but a lesser temporal trend of rate reduction is also evident at least for the women born after 1925. It is then confirmed that the temporal trends of period fertility are the result of the combined effect of the limitation of cohorts' fertility and the decrease in the average age at which women of different cohorts give birth to their children. Over time, large families become less common in favor of the smaller ones - a fact that reflects the general socio-economic transformations observed in the area.

Table 5 – *Period Fertility Rate (TFR) and Average Age at Childbearing (MAC) in the pastoralists and the occupational groups in Metsovo*

Period	Upper town: Pastoralists		Lower town: Occupational groups	
	TFR	MAC	TFR	MAC
1930-1934	4.5	31.6	5.0	31.2
1935-1939	4.1	30.7	4.9	31.4
1940-1944	3.5	30.7	3.4	30.3
1945-1949	3.3	31.3	3.9	30.6
1950-1954	2.9	31.2	3.3	30.2
1955-1959	2.5	29.9	2.7	27.9
1960-1964	2.9	27.9	2.4	27.6
1965-1969	2.5	27.2	2.4	26.4
1970-1974	1.9	26.4	1.7	25.9
1975-1979	1.9	26.7	1.7	24.4
1980-1984	2.1	26.1	1.3	25.3
1985-1989	1.9	27.9	1.2	23.7
1990-1994	1.3	27.1	1.1	24.7
1995-1999	1.3	25.6	1.0	26

The general trend of fertility which diminishes over time to lowest low levels observed in the overall population in 1995-1999 is found both in the upper and lower parts of the town (Table 5). However, in the 1930s, the fertility of the occupational groups was somewhat higher than that of the Pastoralists. Both populations converged in 1940-1944 but in 1945-1949 fertility increased in the occupational groups, while decreasing slightly in the pastoralists' and the difference among them becoming 0.6 children per woman. Afterwards, until 1955-1959, a slightly higher fertility is observed in the

lower town. Fertility increased temporarily in 1960-1964 in the upper part but in the next period both parts of the town converged once again. An important difference in the demographic transition among the two parts of the town is found in the 1970s and 1980s. In the lower town, a stepwise trend reduces fertility to 1.2 children in 1985-1989. In comparison, in the upper town fertility remains at 1.9 children or more by that time. Finally, in both populations fertility becomes very low in the 1990s. *MAC* trends largely follow those of the overall population, but after the 1970s a more variable picture emerges. The most important finding for that period is that in the lower town *MAC* increases after 1985-1989, which means that a postponement of childbearing may have occurred and this depresses further the fertility rates. The opposite is found for the upper town since the 1980s. However, we have to note that in the later periods of study the originally formed population groups have been distorted, because many of their members have changed occupation. In any case, these trends almost surely reflect the structural changes that occurred in the micro society and economy of Metsovo through time and will be briefly discussed later.

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Period fertility in Metsovo declined from more than 4.4 children in the 1930s to 1.2 in 1995-1999, reaching what Kohler *et al.* (2002) called lowest low fertility. The fertility trends in upper and lower town are in accordance with the general trend of the overall population. However, some differences were found among them during the transition course. In the overall population the contribution of older women to the *TFR* becomes gradually less significant and fertility rates decline as the higher order births decline and stabilize at very low levels, which is in accordance with the findings of van de Kaa (2001) for the second demographic transition. During that course the mean age at childbearing for overall births declined until 1975-1979 and increased later. The postponement of first births which is observed after 1975-1979 suppressed the observed period fertility, as is also the case for 3rd order births.

Cohort fertility decreased from 4.5 children per woman in the older cohorts to 1.8 for the cohort of 1945-1949 with a parallel decline of the mean age at childbearing. During that course older women over time contribute to a lesser degree to the observed fertility levels. Then the mechanism of fertility limitation mainly deals with the gradual and voluntary restraint of the upper limit of reproduction of women and the decrease in the size of the families.

Very briefly, the fertility transition in Metsovo must be attributed to the socioeconomic transformations (see Caldwell, 2001; Vézina *et al.*, 2014; Breschi *et al.*, 2014) which occurred in the population and the historical momentum of each epoch. Pastoralism progressively led to stagnation in Metsovo and in 1981 only 7.6% of the population of the whole Municipality

were employed in the agricultural-livestock sector (EL.STAT, Census of agriculture and livestock 1999/2000). The merchants, who used to travel among the Balkans and sell their products, underwent a severe economic crisis as the Balkan States gradually impeded free trade. The other traditional occupational groups, because of the industrialization of the country, lost their validity along with their share in the local, national and international markets.

Meanwhile, the historical momentum of 1940-1949 (see Clogg, 1995, pp. 127-151) and the accompanying economic stagnation resulted in the decline of fertility to only 2.5-2.6 children per woman in the 1960s. No Baby Boom (van Bavel, 2014) was then observed in Metsovo. Instead, the decline of fertility continued in order for a lowest low fertility regime to emerge as the town moved to a new socio-economic environment. As time passed, more advanced economic activities appeared with the establishment of small industries and crafts for the processing of local products, greatly helping in the rapidly developing tourist sector of the economy of Metsovo. In that way in 2008, 15 hotels were found in the town along with 134 stores and offices and 75 small industries (EL.STAT, statistical database 2013).

Cultural diffusion processes (see Knodel and Van de Walle, 1986; Cleland and Wilson, 1987) in combination with the socio-economic transformations, improvements in the level of education (see Becker, 1981; Basu, 2002; Bagavos, 2010; Yoo, 2014) of the population and the alteration of gender roles (see Basu, 1998; Das Gupta, 2013) played an important role too. The gradual arsis of the cultural isolation of the area was accompanied by a reduction in endogamy and alteration of the type of domestic organization and of the role of and the demands on the children through the action of social networks (see Bernardi and Klaerner, 2014). The extended family (see Kaser, 1994; 2012), which was the hegemonic practice in the past, was abandoned in favour of the more modern form of nuclear family: in 2001, 80% of households were of one nuclear family and only 3% of them multi-nuclear ones (EL.STAT, statistical database 2013). Additionally, the adoption of modern market economy by the population increased the cost of the children and decreased their utilitarian value in domestic production (see Nauck, 2014; Werding, 2014).

In 1928, in the province of Metsovo, 82.5% of males aged more than 15 years were literate. On the contrary, 67% of females were illiterate (SGG, 1935, own calculations). This fact is connected with the gender roles in the Pindus Mountains. Males, as representatives of their family had to know how to read and write. Females, on the other hand were supposed to serve the family fulfilling their constructed social role. The pre-arranged marriage and the patrivirilocal system integrated women in their new family under the strict supervision of their husband and their mother in law. In this context they were asked strictly to perform their biological role as mothers and to fulfil their pre-arranged duties in family and production. In 2001, despite continuing differences in the

gender roles, such discrimination against women did not exist, their role changed as they became active members of the market economy and the education level of the population rose (4 PhD holders, 10 with Master's degree, 7,5% with university degree; EL.STAT, 2013), all of them negatively associated with fertility levels.

Overall, fertility levels in Metsovo maintain over time a dynamic character imposed by the changing local structures, which, in their turn, are part of broader national and hyper-national ones.

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